

WAYS TO IMPROVE THE DIGITAL ECONOMY AND TRANSITION TO ELECTRONIC GOVERNMENT IN OUR COUNTRY

Tashkent State University of Economics
“Economic theory” department
professor i.f.d. (DSc) Topildiev S.R.

Tashkent State University of Economics
“Economic theory” department
docent (PhD) Odilova D.B.

Annotation

This article examines the mechanisms for implementing the tasks set in the Digital Uzbekistan 2030 Strategy. The development of the digital economy and e-government is substantiated, serious attention is paid to the IT sphere. At the same time, it is proposed to accelerate the implementation of modern digital technologies that meet the requirements of the present time.

Keywords: technologies, globalization, IT park, resident, IT companies, software products, logistics, robotics, ERP, MES, SCADA, artificial intelligence.

INTRODUCTION

In global practice, the share of the digital economy in the gross domestic product is considered one of the indicators of countries' development. Naturally, this indicator is high in developed countries.

The share of the digital economy in GDP is 10.9% in the USA, 10% in China, 5.5% in India, while in Uzbekistan it does not exceed 2% . The development of this sphere is becoming a modern requirement.

The new economic policy launched in our country in 2017 emphasized the need for digitalization of all sectors and industries in Uzbekistan. The socio-economic development and future prosperity of the Republic of Uzbekistan is organized around economic management based on science, scientific, social, humanitarian and digital technologies. This system is characterized by the rapid development of digital

technologies, the information revolution and the acceleration of economic globalization processes.

Today, digital technologies are actively penetrating all spheres of modern society, including the economy. Digitalization of the economy is becoming an important factor in economic growth in the global economy. In order to ensure accelerated digital development of economic sectors, the social sphere and the public administration system in Uzbekistan, including further improvement of mechanisms for the provision of electronic public services, the Digital Uzbekistan-2030 strategy has been developed. Successful implementation of this strategy and ensuring the achievement of the set goals require analytical and scientific-methodological research, innovative changes. Such changes require theoretical and analytical knowledge about the essence, structure and features of the development of the digital economy.

Level of study of the problem . Among foreign scholars, Niebel (2018) studied the impact of ICT on economic growth in countries with different levels of development, Bahrini and Kaffas (2019) found that broadband and Internet access are a key factor in economic growth in developing countries in Africa and that mobile adoption has a positive impact on economic growth in African countries, and Movella et al. (2020) studied the positive relationship between digitalization and economic growth in a large-scale study from 2006 to 2016 in 41 sub-Saharan African countries and 33 OECD countries.

From Russian scientists Kokurkhaeva Radimkhan Magomet-Bashirovna, Gazdieva Elizaveta Khasbulatovna (2022) Digital sociology - Kelajak sociology, Alekseeva Yu.A., Feofilova T.Yu. (2022) Digital sociology: theory and practice, Gusarova O.M., Kondrashov V.M., Ganicheva E.IN. (2022) Digital resources of Zamonaviy Zhamiyatning: domestic and foreign experience, Dolgikh E.A. , Pershina T.A. (2022) analyzed the formation of a digital society in European countries.

Among our Uzbek scientists, Academician Gulomov S.S. studied the widespread use of electronic and information and telecommunication technologies in the economy (2019), Makhmudova G.N. (2021) Structural changes in the context of modernization and digitalization of the Uzbek economy, digitalization of the banking system,

<https://president.uz/uz/lists/view/3848>

Makhmudova G.N., Ashurov Z.A., Razikova B.S. (2022) conducted scientific research on the development of the digital ecosystem in Uzbekistan.

Research methodology . The methodology of the article begins with the analysis of scientific and increasingly popular sources, the new economic policy in the republic today, comprehensive programs and applications for the digitalization of all sectors and industries of Uzbekistan, generalization of economic experience in the use of modern web tools to improve the efficiency of innovation, interviews with investors on the problem of this study.

Foreign, Russian and Uzbek scientists and specialists in the context of innovative development took part in the preparation of the article . The new economic policy used scientific research to urgently implement digitalization of all sectors and industries in Uzbekistan.

Analysis and results . Taking into account the above, in order to implement reforms in this area, on April 8, 2020, the Presidential Decree "On measures for the widespread introduction of the digital economy and e-government" was adopted. At the same time, the resolution also clearly indicates the sources of financing for new projects. Within the framework of the "e-government", it is planned to implement 104 projects worth 1.3 trillion soums, in the real sector of the economy - 87 projects worth 5.3 trillion soums, in telecommunications - 35 projects worth 15.1 trillion soums , in the agro-industrial complex - 24, in IT parks - 18 projects ².

As a result of serious attention to the IT sector, certain changes have been achieved over the past three years. In particular, last year, IT Park residents provided services worth 5 trillion soums (2.5 trillion soums in 2021) and exported services worth 140 million US dollars (50 million US dollars in 2021).

At the same time, 370 of the existing 715 public services were transferred to a digital platform, and 12 million people used these services last year (compared to 9 million in 2021).

As a result of digitalization, the requirement for the provision of more than 70 types of information and documents from the population has been cancelled.

In the future, it is planned to increase the export of IT services to \$1 billion. Including:

²Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 8, 2020 No. PP-4699 "On measures for the widespread introduction of the digital economy and electronic government."

- the need for at least 100,000 qualified programmers, IT architects, operators and engineers;
- expansion of high-speed Internet and conditions for specialists in the regions; the need to create a more favorable environment for the growth of foreign IT companies;
- creation of a system for training personnel in modern IT professions;
- It is advisable to launch at least 200 new electronic services that are most in demand by the population and entrepreneurs.

Our country is implementing comprehensive measures to actively develop the digital economy, the widespread introduction of modern information and communication technologies in all sectors and areas, primarily in public administration, education, healthcare and agriculture.

In particular, the implementation of more than 220 priority projects has begun, including the improvement of the electronic government system, the further development of the local market for software products and information technologies, the creation of IT parks in all regions of the republic, and the provision of the industry with qualified personnel.

In addition, a comprehensive program “Digital Tashkent” is being implemented, which involves the launch of a geoportal integrated with more than 40 information systems, the creation of an information system for managing public transport and communal infrastructure, digitalization of the social sphere, as well as the subsequent implementation of this experience in other regions.

In order to develop digital technologies in the real sector of the economy, it is necessary to implement the following measures, including:

- combining programs for the implementation of modern information technologies in industrial enterprises with programs for the technological re-equipment of these enterprises;
- ensuring automation and management of all stages of enterprise supply, as well as reducing logistics and procurement costs as a result;
- improving the quality of products and services, reducing their cost, production downtime, increasing the transparency of financial and economic activities through the introduction of modern information systems and software products;
- improving the regulatory framework for the implementation of innovative automated control systems and software products;

- gradual automation of workplaces and robotization of production processes, as well as the introduction of artificial intelligence technologies;
- Improving mechanisms of interaction with customers (clients) in order to increase sales volumes and improve the quality of customer service;
- improvement of the information support system for management, including the introduction of a real-time business analysis system;
- Increase the share of large business entities that have implemented an enterprise resource planning (ERP) system to 90% by 2025;
- localization of the software part of technologies for automation of production and management processes (ERP, MES, SCADA, etc.), robotics, the Internet of Things, artificial intelligence at industrial enterprises by 2027, and the hardware part by 2030 on the basis of public-private partnership;
- implementation of intelligent technologies for managing utility payments, implementation of intelligent services and implementation of the “smart home” experience for regulating utility services;
- in 2022, an automated payment system for public transport was introduced in all major cities of the republic, and the share of cashless payments was increased to 90%;
- creation of a single platform for purchasing tickets for any passenger transport;
- expansion of sales markets for products and services produced by enterprises via the Internet;
- implementation of mechanisms for using software modeling systems for the integrated development of the transport system;
- development and implementation of mechanisms for the introduction of digital insurance based on public-private partnerships with the aim of digitalizing the insurance system;
- gradual transition to a digital logistics system in order to improve the logistics system and introduce digital technologies;
- development and implementation of robotics in real sectors of the economy;
- organization of robotics and engineering specialties for large industrial enterprises;
- It is necessary to widely implement additive technologies (layer-by-layer construction and synthesis technologies, 3D printing) in manufacturing enterprises.

In order to develop the system of electronic commerce and electronic payments, it is advisable to implement the following measures, in particular:

- development of remote banking services through the introduction of information and communication technologies, including remote client identification systems;

- improvement and updating of the regulatory framework for the development of electronic commerce, as well as current standards and rules of electronic commerce in order to comply with international standards of electronic commerce and modern requirements of information security;

- development of digital infrastructure, expansion of the possibilities and scale of connection to e-commerce platforms from personal digital devices by further increasing the coverage and speed of the global information network of mobile and wired Internet;

- further development of electronic commerce and electronic payment systems, as well as improvement of the information infrastructure in the economic and financial spheres, taking into account the possibilities of receiving and processing payments when providing electronic government services;

- ensuring the modernization and technical renewal of the postal and logistics infrastructure, which plays an important role in the development of electronic commerce, the implementation of large projects to create logistics centers (fulfillment), the introduction of information technologies and automated systems at postal facilities, as well as improving the quality of postal and logistics services;

- development of payment aggregators that allow individuals to simplify the process of organizing payments for goods and services via the Internet;

- develop cross-border e-commerce and ensure convenient and timely export of products from local manufacturers;

- creation of a business model of financial supermarkets aimed at providing a wide range of banking and non-banking financial services (securities transactions, insurance, etc.) on a single trading platform;

- expansion of the volume and improvement of the quality of services provided by commercial banks to clients through remote banking systems (Internet banking, bank-client, SMS banking, etc.), including the use of mobile applications;

- electronic transactions and in the field of malakali personnel trained to improve the quality and quality of education, retraining of specialists and improving the quality

of education, including foreign leaders in the field of science and technology. attracting foreign specialists;

- creation of the possibility of accepting payments for goods and services by e-commerce entities using modern and convenient remote methods through the introduction of QR payment technology and NFC technologies, including accepting payments using mobile devices;

- the development and wider use of e-commerce and digital payment platforms should be supported in close cooperation between the public sector, local authorities and the private sector³.

The world is rapidly changing under the influence of digital technologies. Digital technologies have penetrated into all spheres of state activity, and the development and competitiveness of any state in the world community depend on the effective development of information technologies. It is the rapid development of modern digital technologies and the creation of all the necessary conditions for this that is one of the priorities of state policy.

Target indicators of "the Digital Strategy "Uzbekistan - 2030"

T/p	Index name	Unit of measurement	Current status	Goals for these years		
				2022	2025	2030
1	The length of the fiber-optic communication network built in the republic	thousand km	41	70	120	250
2	The level of coverage of the regions of the republic with high-speed Internet and the global information network	percent	67	74	85	100

³<https://lex.uz/docs/5030957?ONDATE=14.07.2021&ONDATE2=31.10.2020&action=compare>. Decree No. PF-6079 of October 5, 2020 on approval of the Digital Uzbekistan-2030 strategy and measures for its effective implementation.

⁴President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Decree No. UF-6079 of October 5, 2020 "On approval of the strategy " Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" and measures for its effective implementation."

3	Level of provision of social facilities with high-speed Internet access	percent	45	100	100	100
4	Household broadband internet access levels	percent	67	74	85	100
5	Level of coverage of populated areas by broadband mobile networks	percent	78	100	100	100
6	The E-Government Development Index performance index in the international e-government development rating	Score (between 0-1)	0.66	0.70	0.75	0.86
7	The share of public services in electronic form provided through the Unified Portal of Interactive Public Services, relative to public services provided by public service centers	percent	34	60	70	90
8	The share of e-government services available via mobile devices relative to e-government services on the Unified Portal of Interactive Government Services	percent	5	30	42	60
9	The share of transactional services provided through the unified interactive portal of public services	interest	25	45	60	75
10	The share of large enterprises that have implemented an	interest	20	40	65	100

	enterprise resource planning (ERP) system					
11	Number of users of Internet banking services (legal entities and individuals)	million people	10	15	17	20
12	Number of startup projects included in the incubation and acceleration programs of the technology park of educational and methodological products and information technologies	piece	50	250	700	2 300
13	The number of control figures for admission to higher and secondary specialized educational institutions for training personnel in the field of information technology	thousand	7	12	15	20

The implementation of tasks and plans for digitalization for 2023, the fact that 34 services in the internal affairs bodies, 32 in the justice bodies, 29 in "Uzstandard", 11 in healthcare, which are most in demand by the population, are not transferred to electronic form, leads to confusion among the population. For example, to obtain a medical certificate "form 086", which is necessary for employment or study, or to obtain a driver's license, people are forced to go to the clinic every time. Obtaining a medical certificate "form 086" must be electronically placed in the citizen's medical record at the clinic, and citizens will be able to receive a medical certificate in electronic form and provide it to the requested address, wherever they are. An application for land privatization is submitted online. However, since the data in the public utilities sector is not digitized, subsequent stages are still carried out based on the "manual" human factor. Or more than 300 thousand buyers buy a new car per year. However, to register and receive a state registration plate, you still need to contact the road safety service.

The President noted that other ministries have not yet created a digitalization system that would satisfy our people ⁵.

In our opinion, the "Digital Economy" is capable of uniting the state, business and science. To achieve integration with other international systems and mechanisms of functioning in the digital economy, the data and document models in the "single window" mechanism should be organized on the basis of international standards and recommendations. When forming a list of data, including the initial data of messages and documents subject to integration, as well as when forming a national data model, it is necessary to describe and define them in accordance with the requirements of international standards.

Conclusion . To summarize, we can say that as a result of the full and high-quality implementation of the Strategy "Digital Uzbekistan 2030", the following results will be achieved . Including:

1. It is necessary to provide competitive communications and telecommunications, all social facilities with the Internet, expand fiber-optic communication networks throughout the republic, increase the coverage of populated areas with high-speed communication technologies (5G and others), and reduce the digital gap between cities and villages.

2. It is necessary to become one of the most developed countries in the international ranking, increase the share of electronic government services, ensure safe and convenient interaction of the population with government bodies, develop electronic government, effectively distribute and use computing power based on the needs of the state, business and the population.

3. It is advisable to increase the number of residents of IT parks throughout the country, improve the investment climate, and increase the efficiency of investments in the field of information technology.

4. It is necessary to create broad opportunities for all segments of the population to receive education in the field of information technology, to form a reserve of professional personnel in the field of information technology and a reserve of management personnel, and to develop skills in using the tools of the digital economy and e-government.

⁵ https://uza.uz/uz/posts/digitalization-boyicha-hali-xalqimizni-rozi-kilidagan-tizim-toliq-yartilmeli_456682

5. It is proposed to implement the goals and objectives set in the Digital Uzbekistan-2030 Strategy in a timely and high-quality manner, to increase the number of graduates of higher educational institutions in the field of IT, to create training centers for digital technologies in all districts (cities, villages) of the republic.

In order to further develop the digital economy, special attention should be paid to the following areas:

1. It is necessary to create sufficient conditions for a full transition to a digital economy. Including:

- creation of new information and communication technologies;
- development of computer literacy in the country;
- increase the number of qualified personnel working in this field;
- ensuring the use of the digital economy in all industries and sectors of the republic;
- ensuring full and high-quality access to Internet services in remote areas of the country.

2. It is also important to explain to the public that the digital economy is not only about blockchain technologies and cryptocurrencies.

3. It is necessary to develop and implement measures to stimulate and support competition among online traders, as well as its further development.

4. It is advisable to attract young personnel to this area and provide them with training and advanced training in foreign universities that are developing in the field of the “Digital Economy” in order to create an infrastructure for achieving high results.

5. It is necessary to attract highly qualified foreign specialists to the industry.

Today, in the conditions of Uzbekistan, it is extremely important to study the patterns, trends and possibilities of the development of the digital economy on a scientific basis, in particular, the degree of penetration of information technologies into various sectors of the economy. The development and prospects of our Motherland, the success of large-scale reforms carried out in our country directly depend on the introduction of new innovations into our national economy. Therefore, the development of the digital economy, its economic, political, social and legal foundations are of great importance from the point of view of scientific and practical research.

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